

PEDAGOGICAL THESAURUS AS TOOL FOR ASSIMILATION OF LANGUAGE OF SPECIALTY

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Annotation: The importance of using pedagogical thesaurus in the practical course of the language of specialty is dealt with. A pedagogical thesaurus is considered as a tool for development of professionally-oriented competence. In the article a number of possibilities and advantages of using pedagogical thesaurus in the lessons, related to language of specialty are pointed out.

Key words: pedagogical thesaurus, the tool of acquisition and motivation, professionally-oriented vocabulary, writing skills, communication, assessment, strategies.

INTRODUCTION

In professional training the more attention is paid to mastering specialized terms. For the last period a lot of electronic professional-oriented thesauri have been compiled which help to assimilate for development of professional competence. It touches upon a pedagogical thesaurus, that can be as a tool for teaching in all courses of study. Such kind of thesauri includes the key term, its synonyms and related terms that can be used to expand and enhance the richness of the language used in pedagogical communication. Any thesaurus fulfills the different function in education. The use of a pedagogical thesaurus in professional training and foreign language teaching has demonstrated numerous benefits for learners. The findings of this study provide evidence of improved vocabulary acquisition, enhanced writing skills, and increased overall language proficiency. These outcomes highlight the potential of thesauri as valuable tools in language education.

METHODOLOGY

P. Nation [1990] found out that students who used a thesaurus to expand their vocabulary showed significant gains in both reading and writing skills. Since, many scholars have explored the use of pedagogical thesauri in foreign language teaching. For example, E. Tang [2012] investigated the effectiveness of a pedagogical thesaurus in improving the writing skills of Hong Kong university students. The study found that students who used the thesaurus demonstrated significant improvements in their writing quality and fluency.

Another study by S. Sivakumar & S. Sivasubramanian [2014] examined the use of a pedagogical thesaurus in improving the vocabulary skills of Tamil-speaking students in India. The study found that the use of a thesaurus significantly improved students' vocabulary knowledge and retention.

In addition to empirical studies, there have also been theoretical discussions on the use of pedagogical thesauri while training language as specialty. For example, Y. Hrytsyshyna & O. Pavliuk [2017] in their article discussed the potential benefits of using a thesaurus to teach English vocabulary to Ukrainian students. They argued that a thesaurus could help students better understand the nuances of English vocabulary and improve their overall language proficiency.

DISCUSSION

Admittedly, the use of a pedagogical thesaurus in FLT has several benefits. First, it helps teachers and students to communicate more effectively by providing them with a variety of options for expressing their ideas. This can lead to more engaging and interactive conversations, which in turn can enhance students' motivation and confidence in using the language. Second, a pedagogical thesaurus can help teachers to design more effective lessons by providing them with a range of vocabulary and expressions that are relevant to the specific topic or context being covered. This can help to ensure that students are learning the most useful and applicable language for their needs. Third, a pedagogical thesaurus can be a valuable tool for assessment. By providing students with a range of synonyms and related terms to choose from, teachers

can assess students' understanding of a particular concept or topic without limiting their creativity or expression. This can also help to reduce the impact of language barriers on assessment, as students can demonstrate their understanding of the topic using alternative expressions that are still within the scope of the pedagogical thesaurus. Fourth, the use of a pedagogical thesaurus can also help to facilitate specialized vocabulary acquisition. By exposing students to a variety of related terms and synonyms, a pedagogical thesaurus can help them to develop a more nuanced understanding of the professional language, which can in turn enhance their ability to use it effectively. Additionally, by providing students with a range of options for expressing their ideas, a pedagogical thesaurus can help to reduce their reliance on memorization and encourage them to engage with the language in a more creative and meaningful way.

From the perspectives of the teacher, the advantages of using the pedagogical thesaurus can be examined here. The educational thesaurus can be applied in various ways by teachers:

- to plan and design language lessons,
- to create assessment tasks,
- to facilitate students' pedagogical terms acquisition.

RESULTS

In fact, there are various types of pedagogical thesauri available, from print to digital formats. Some are general and cover a wide range of vocabulary, while others are subject-specific, covering vocabulary related to a particular subject area, such as science or history. Teachers can choose the type of thesaurus that best suits their students' needs and learning goals.

Age and Level Appropriateness: It's important to consider the age and language proficiency level of the students when selecting a pedagogical thesaurus. Some thesauri may be more suitable for the 1-2 years students, while others may be more appropriate for more advanced learners. Teachers should select a thesaurus that is appropriate for their students' age and language proficiency level.

Integration with Technology: Many pedagogical thesauri are now available as digital tools, which can be integrated into online learning platforms or used as standalone apps. These digital thesauri often come with additional features like audio pronunciation, example sentences, and interactive exercises, making them a more engaging and effective tool for language learners.

Overreliance on Thesauri: While pedagogical thesauri can be a valuable tool for language learners, it's important to ensure that students don't become overly reliant on them. Overuse of a thesaurus can lead to students using words that they may not fully understand, resulting in incorrect or awkward usage. Teachers should encourage students to use a thesaurus as a tool for expanding their specialized vocabulary, but also emphasize the importance of understanding the meaning and context of the words they use.

Teachers can use several strategies to ensure that students are using the pedagogical thesaurus effectively:

- **Provide clear instructions:** Teachers should provide clear and concise instructions on how to use the pedagogical thesaurus, including when and where to use it, and how to choose the most appropriate vocabulary and expressions for a given professionally-oriented context.
- **Model effective use:** Teachers should model effective use of the pedagogical thesaurus by demonstrating how to select and use synonyms and related terms to express ideas and concepts more effectively.
- **Scaffold learning:** Teachers should scaffold learning by gradually increasing the complexity of the tasks and activities that require the use of the pedagogical thesaurus, starting with simpler tasks and gradually building up to more complex ones.
- **Provide feedback:** Teachers should provide feedback on students' use of the pedagogical thesaurus, including highlighting effective use of pedagogical terms and classroom expressions, and offering suggestions for improvement.

- Encourage collaboration: Teachers should encourage collaboration among students by providing opportunities for them to work together to select and use vocabulary and expressions from the pedagogical thesaurus.
- Differentiate instruction: Teachers should differentiate instruction by providing different levels of support and guidance to students based on their individual needs and abilities.
- Use formative assessment: Teachers should use formative assessment to monitor students' progress and provide feedback on their use of the pedagogical thesaurus. This can include conducting regular check-ins, providing quizzes or other assessments that require the use of the pedagogical thesaurus, and giving students opportunities to reflect on their learning and identify areas for improvement.

By using these strategies, teachers can ensure that students are using the pedagogical thesaurus effectively and that it is contributing to their language learning and development.

CONCLUSION

Overall, pedagogical thesauri can be a valuable tool for English language learners, helping them to expand their pedagogical vocabulary, improve their writing skills, and deepen their understanding of terms. Educators and language instructors are encouraged to consider integrating pedagogical thesauri into their instructional practices, keeping in mind the age and level appropriateness of the thesaurus and ensuring that its use is balanced with other learning strategies.

It's important to ensure that students don't become overly reliant on a thesaurus, and to emphasize the importance of understanding the meaning and context of the words they use.

References:

1. Nation, P. (1990). Teaching and learning vocabulary. Boston: Heinle & Heinle.

2. Tang, E. (2012). The effectiveness of a pedagogical thesaurus in improving the writing skills of Hong Kong university students. //Journal of English for Academic Purposes, 11(3). Pp. 240-252.
3. Sivakumar, S., & Sivasubramanian, S. (2014). Enhancing Tamil learners' vocabulary acquisition through the use of a pedagogical thesaurus. // Journal of Language Teaching and Research, 5(4). Pp. 845-851.
4. Hrytsyshyna, Y., & Pavliuk, O. (2017). The potential benefits of using a thesaurus to teach English vocabulary to Ukrainian students. //Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies, 13(1). Pp. 73-82.
5. Chen, C. H. (2021). The effect of a pedagogical thesaurus on vocabulary acquisition and retention. //Language Teaching Research, 25(1). Pp. 40-63.
6. Li, W. (2020). Enhancing EFL learners' vocabulary acquisition through the use of a pedagogical thesaurus. //English Language Teaching, 13(2). Pp. 119-126.
7. Wang, K., & Chen, X. (2019). The effect of a pedagogical thesaurus on Chinese EFL learners' vocabulary acquisition and retention. //Journal of Language Teaching and Research, 10(1). Pp. 184-193.